

solid compound even after four to five hours; only a very thin white film was observed on the side of the beaker. After 24 hours the solution became more dense, viscous and turbid, but there was no solid phase. No solid phase appeared even after 48 hours. After three days a solid separated out which was filtered, washed and dried as before. The properties of this compound were also similar.

Compound (I) is most probably $SbCl_3(NH_3)_3.H_2O$ with a small amount of the compound (II) which is $SbCl_3(NH_3)_2.H_2O$. The compound (III) is probably formed due to absorption of water besides the absorption of ammonia, and since the concentration of water vapour is small compared to that of ammonia inside the bell jar, the formation of this compound is slow. The complex (III) is therefore, $SbCl_3.NH_3.H_2O$. It is of interest to note that the complex (III), which is formed after three days, contains only one molecule of ammonia per atom of antimony, whereas, the other two, which are comparatively quickly formed under similar conditions, contain more ammonia. The ammonia and water molecules are strongly bound as they are not lost over concentrated sulphuric acid (the compound II when kept over sulphuric acid lost 0.03% in weight after three months).

These compounds are possibly co-ordination complexes.

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EFFECT OF AZOTOBACTER ON FIXED NITROGEN

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The utilisation of fixed nitrogen by *Azotobacter vinelandii* has been investigated by using a colorimetric method. It has been found that only those nitrogenous compounds are utilised by the bacteria which are likely to be reduced to ammonia, and that the lag period of the bacteria in case of compounds utilised increases with increase of concentration.

Horner (*J. Bakt.*, 1944, 47, 1) and Rosenblum (*ibid.*, 1952, 61, 475) investigated the effect of various nitrogenous compounds including amino-acids, amines, amides, glyco-coll, urea and hydrazine on the growth and nitrogen-fixing activities of azotobacter. They found that with the exception of urea these were not as readily utilised as the inorganic ammonium salts and nitrates.

Fuller and Rettger (*Soil Sci.*, 1931, 31, 219) observed that more complex organic compounds were not easily attacked by azotobacter and consequently the growth and nitrogen-fixing activity of the organism were not much influenced.

Lewis and Hinshelwood (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 824) and Azim and Roberts (*Biochim. biophys. Acta*, 1955, 18, 363) have established that inorganic ammonium salts, nitrates and nitrites are utilised by *Azotobacter vinelandii*.

Thus, those nitrogenous compounds, which are reduced to ammonia, are likely to be utilised by azotobacter, and this view conforms with the ammonia hypothesis of biological fixation of atmospheric nitrogen (Wilson, *Ann. Rev. Biochem.*, 1945, 14 685). In order to confirm our own point of view we undertook to investigate a few organic and inorganic nitrogenous compounds like potassium nitrate and amyl nitrite, which are reduceable to ammonia, and some other compounds like nitrobenzene, aniline and sodium azide, which are not reduceable to ammonia, and we found our hypothesis to be correct.

Various workers investigated the utilisation of compounds without studying their relation with concentration. We have therefore attempted to investigate the speed of utilisation at different initial concentrations and have obtained a relation between concentration and the lag period of the bacteria.

Procedure.—The flasks containing identical volumes of the sterile culture medium inoculated with a known population of *A. vinelandii*, usually about 109 cells per 25 c.c., were incubated at 30°. The calculated volume of standard substrate solution was added to the culture medium so as to attain the desired concentration ($10^{-4} M$ to $10^{-2} M$). A known volume of the test solution was withdrawn by means of a pipette and analysed by the usual colorimetric methods (nitrate with phenol disulphonic acid, nitrite with Griess Hoesva's reagent, aniline with bleaching powder and azide with ferric chloride).

TABLE I
% Utilisation.

Time.	Potassium nitrate.			Amyl nitrite.			Time.	Pot. nitrate		Amyl nitrite.	
	$10^{-2} M$.	$10^{-3} M$.	$10^{-4} M$.	$10^{-3} M$.	$10^{-4} M$.	$10^{-3} M$.		$10^{-2} M$.	$10^{-4} M$.		
0.0 hr.	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	7.0 hr.	0.0	82.2	0.0	0.0
1.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	7.5	5.4	100.0	0.0	0.0
2.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	9.1	8.0	0.7	...	...	0.0
2.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	19.6	8.5	21.7	...	...	0.8
2.75	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	58.8	9.0	...	...	...	13.3
3.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.9	100.0	10.0	32.5	...	...	36.8
3.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	4.0	...	10.5	48.7	...	...	69.4
4.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	11.8	...	11.5	62.2	...	...	...
4.5	0.0	14.3	0.0	0.0	37.5	...	12.0	...	...	...	100.0
5.0	0.0	28.6	0.0	0.0	100.0	...	12.5	83.8	...	...	...
6.5	0.0	71.5	...	...	...	...	13.5	100.0	...	...	...

The utilisation of potassium nitrate, amyl nitrite, nitrobenzene, aniline and sodium azide by *Vinelandii* was studied at different concentrations ranging from $10^{-4} M$ to $10^{-2} M$. Potassium nitrate and amyl nitrite were found to be utilised in solutions lower than $2 \times 10^{-2} M$ concentrations, while in stronger solutions they were neither utilised nor were found to be toxic. It is clear from the table that the lag period

required by azotobacter¹ to start utilisation of nitrates and nitrite increases with increase of concentration and after the expiry of the lag period, the rate of utilisation increases with increase of concentration. Nitrobenzene, aniline and sodium azide were not utilised even at lower concentrations. From these results it is concluded that nitrobenzene, aniline and azide although containing the same groups as of nitrite and ammonia are not utilised because they are not reducible to ammonia and thus the ammonia hypothesis of nitrogen fixation has been confirmed.

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